

MobiSpaces End-User Workshop

Realising Innovation: Bridging Theory to Impactful Solutions

iRoute

SmartSense

MarineTrafficTracker

VesselEdge

CrowdSeaMapping

Funded by
the European Union

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Realising Innovation: Bridging Theory to Impactful Solutions

The [MobiSpaces End-User workshop](#), held on **29 February 2024**, was a pivotal event showcasing the achievements and impacts of each project's use case. It aimed to demonstrate the practical applications and societal significance of MobiSpaces' developed components through real-time demos. Attendees gained insights into the objectives of MobiSpaces use cases via practical demonstrations, highlighting the crafted components and their societal implications.

MobiSpaces: an EU-funded project for sustainable mobility data solutions

The workshop began with *Matteo Falsetta*, *EU Programme Manager at GFT Technologies and Project Manager for MobiSpaces*, providing an overview of the **project's goals**.

MobiSpaces aims to revolutionise data management in the mobility sector through its innovative platform, which utilises AI-based mobility analytics. By optimising the entire data lifecycle, the project ensures efficiency, security, and sustainability.

Key objectives include establishing effective data governance, reducing carbon footprint, enhancing AI operations, enforcing security and compliance standards, promoting interoperability, and implementing decentralised edge processing.

MobiSpaces demonstrates its capabilities through **five use cases**: *predictive maintenance, intelligent traffic sensing, vessel tracking, edge computing on moving vessels, and crowdsourced nautical mapping*.

The project's main **tech objectives** focus on establishing a reliable data governance platform, implementing green AI-enhanced data management, providing comprehensive analytics solutions, delivering high-performance analytics, and ensuring transparency through explainable AI and federated learning.

Through these use cases and technologies, MobiSpaces aims to transform the mobility sector by offering innovative solutions that optimise data governance and promote sustainability and efficiency.

Driving Green Innovation: Exploring MobiSpaces Use Cases

MobiSpaces use cases showcase practical applications of transportation systems on land and sea. They aim to achieve key objectives: demonstrate technical advancements, validate developed technologies through analysis, and conceptualise scenarios for MobiSpaces' effective utilisation.

iRoute - Intelligent Public Transport Routing

Main Objectives:

During the workshop, *Lorenzo Montero from AMT*, the public transport company of Genova, Italy, shared insights into their collaboration with MobiSpaces. He discussed their focus on integrating electric buses into their fleet and the challenges they encounter, such as battery life and fleet optimisation. Through MobiSpaces, AMT aims to enhance their dataset utilisation to address these challenges effectively.

Benefits of Cooperation with MobiSpaces:

Lorenzo highlighted significant achievements, including improved dataset organisation facilitated by MobiSpaces. By structuring their data and establishing a coherent architecture, AMT gained better insights into fleet management, leading to outcomes like fleet allocation optimisation. Lorenzo showcased a genetic algorithm developed with their technical partner, Engineering, for optimising fleet allocation based on trip

duration and operational needs. Future enhancements will involve integrating battery behaviour data to ensure efficient fleet management and extend battery life.

SmartSense - Intelligent Infrastructure Traffic Sensing

Main objectives

Gabriel Braun, Project Manager at Bosch, presented the second use case, focusing on traffic management and air quality. This initiative utilises smart sensors to collect data for Environmental Sensitive Traffic Management. By integrating smart sensing with a secure data management platform, this use case demonstrates the benefits of advanced sensor technology. Smart sensors interpret diverse signals to provide accurate data for evaluating measures to mitigate noise and air pollution from traffic. Gabriel highlighted the pressing issue of air pollution, citing recent EU regulations aimed at halving emission limits by 2030. The project's test area in Thessaloniki serves as a vital hub for data collection. Strategically positioned air quality sensors generate a real-time heat map visualising pollution levels, providing insights into key air quality metrics.

Benefits of Cooperation with MobiSpaces:

Thanks to MobiSpaces, the team employs sophisticated modelling techniques to analyse traffic emissions, considering factors like vehicle type, speed, and volume. Preliminary results show promising trends, paving the way for further data refinement and the development of targeted traffic management strategies to reduce emissions. The SmartSense use case aims to improve air quality in Thessaloniki by monitoring emission reduction, enhancing transparency, and collaborating with traffic management authorities.

MarineTrafficTracker - Edge-powered Vessel Tracking

Main Objectives:

Konstantina Bereta, Director of Research Lab at Kpler, and Dimitris Vitoris, Research and Development Engineer, jointly presented the developments of the VesselTracker use case within MobiSpaces. This initiative focuses on vessel tracking and detection, aiming to develop a robust vessel tracker capable of multi-sensor, multi-object detection to identify dark targets undetectable by GIS.

Benefits of Cooperation with MobiSpaces:

Implementing the MobiSpaces framework enabled the VesselTracker team to combine results at the edge, reducing data transfer costs to centralised infrastructure. Leveraging edge computing, the project utilises data from AIS and radio frequency (RF) readers to track vessel positions and attributes. The system integrates smart sensors to correlate technical incidents with AIS data in real time, enabling the detection of dark vessels. The workflow involves processing AIS and RF data streams, cleaning data, and performing federated learning for prediction. Through this process, the team aims to improve data-to-object association accuracy and data-to-track success rate.

MarineTrafficTracker

VesselEdge - Edge Computing Onboard of Moving Vessels

Main Objectives:

Presented by *Thomas Graeupl, Corporate Researcher at Frequentis,* the VesselTracker use case focuses on implementing edge computing onboard moving vessels to enhance situational awareness for coastal control centres. The presentation elucidated the concept of edge computing, which involves processing data on vessels rather than at coastal control centres, with the goal of improving control centre situational awareness by processing AIS data from vessels further out at sea. Thomas

VesselEdge

detailed the technical aspects of AIS (Automatic Identification System), its role in vessel tracking, and the challenges of tracking ships beyond the reach of coastal antennas. The Vessel Edge project addresses this challenge by equipping vessels with edge devices to receive AIS signals and relay them to control centres, employing trajectory compression to optimise data transmission and federated learning to enhance anomaly detection. A demonstration showcased anomaly detection and trajectory compression, highlighting the reduction in data transmission volume and the accuracy of the federated learning model compared to centralised models.

Benefits of Cooperating with MobiSpaces:

The collaboration between Frequentis and the project's consortium facilitated the integration of MobiSpaces technologies and methodologies into the VesselEdge use case, fostering the development of innovative solutions for maritime situational awareness. Thomas emphasised the significance of leveraging collective expertise and resources within the MobiSpaces consortium to effectively address complex challenges. Through collaboration and knowledge-sharing within MobiSpaces, the Vessel Edge project aims to advance maritime safety and security by enhancing control centre capabilities and expanding situational awareness beyond coastal regions.

CrowdSeaMapping - Federated Learning for Enhancing Nautical Charts

Main objectives

Niels Bo Nielsen from Danish Geodata

presented the final MobiSpaces use case, focused on enhancing maritime safety through improved navigational charts using modern technology. Drawing a parallel between historical practices of marking dangerous areas with sea monsters and the contemporary need for accurate navigational data, Niels showcased the Danish coastal model, highlighting gaps and interpolation artefacts in the data coverage. Emphasising the

importance of accurate charts for safe navigation, especially in heavily trafficked areas like Denmark, the use case aims to crowdsource depth data, currently available only on echo sounders, and transmit it via edge computing and AI for real-time updates. Given the evolving seafloor landscape poses risks to navigation, up-to-date depth data is crucial. CrowdSeaMapping leverages AIS and depth data for anomaly detection and model verification, incorporating federated learning for privacy and efficiency. The model's training data includes simulated errors and anomalies commonly encountered at sea.

Benefits of Cooperating with MobiSpaces:

The CrowdSeaMapping team plans to integrate hardware and software components through sea trials, leveraging MobiSpaces technologies for enhanced maritime safety. Cooperation with MobiSpaces is pivotal as it provides a platform for data integration, analysis, and visualisation. The project envisions seamless integration of edge computing, AI, and federated learning models within the MobiSpaces platform to bolster navigational safety. By collaborating with MobiSpaces, the project gains access to advanced technologies and expertise to develop efficient solutions for maritime data processing and anomaly detection. This collaboration empowers the project to unlock the full potential of modern technologies and contribute to safer navigation in maritime environments.

Feedback session with the use cases adopters

The workshop concluded with an engaging Q&A session, offering participants the opportunity to address specific inquiries regarding their interest in MobiSpaces use cases and their experiences with similar initiatives. The workshop drew the participation of 61 individuals from 18 countries, with 35 attendees joining virtually. Below is a summary of their expertise and country of origin:

During the session, attendees were asked to respond to questions, including inquiries about the most significant challenges encountered in developing transportation use cases.

Engaging with the participants revealed that experts in the field are actively involved in related areas within MobiSpaces, such as logistics, transportation, software engineering, and smart infrastructure. However, despite their expertise, they expressed a need for suggestions to address the challenges they face.

Join our External Advisory Board and enhance innovation and impact

To overcome challenges in developing MobiSpaces use cases, we're hosting a series of co-creation workshops. Experts from our External Advisory Board will provide valuable feedback on these projects.

These workshops actively involve identified experts who offer insights into use case development. As invited members of the **MobiSpaces External Advisory Board**, these experts play a crucial role in providing strategic guidance for advancing our cutting-edge projects. Their active participation directly influences the trajectory of innovative projects shaping the future of transportation, logistics, software engineering, and smart infrastructure.

Are you ready to contribute to shaping the technical components of MobiSpaces use cases, share best practices, and drive innovation? Don't miss this opportunity to join our External Advisory Board.

[Apply now!](#)

In case you missed it, we invite you to watch the workshop recording on the [MobiSpaces YouTube channel](#).

Follow MobiSpaces on the main project's social media channels and visit the website to follow its technical advancements.

@: [mobispaces.eu](https://www.mobispaces.eu)

X: [@MobiSpaces](https://twitter.com/MobiSpaces)

in: [/company/mobispaces](https://www.linkedin.com/company/mobispaces)

▶: [MobiSpaces](https://www.youtube.com/MobiSpaces)

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